

INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION IN THE FIELD OF OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY IN UZBEKISTAN

ISMOILOV SUNNATILLA ISHOQOVICH

Researcher of the National university of Uzbekistan

Abstract: The economic independence of the country which is associated with the production of competitive products and providing the most important priority in the comprehensive development of the mutually beneficial cooperation in the oil and gas industry plays an important role. In this article are analyzed the issues of cooperation in the field of oil and gas industry in the years of independence

Keywords: Beneficial cooperation, Tokyo, presentation of hydrocarbon deposits, artificial liquid fuel

As it is known, from the first years of its independence, Uzbekistan and national all sectors of the economy and the development of radical reforms to strengthen and establish mutually beneficial cooperation with foreign countries and companies in the implementation of important events in the field on a consistent basis has been implemented. In this regard the main directions and tasks defined by the government of the republic is the exact purpose of this function is to be made in the interests of the various foreign countries, as well as advanced technology and network with companies who have a great experience is important in the development of mutually beneficial cooperation in the international community[1].

Oil and gas cooperation in the development of the economy of the network at the launch of the initiative of the government of the republic of Houston with us in July 1996, the city of Tokyo in Japan in the month of December of Uzbekistan in the oil and gas potential of the presentation[2]'s the importance of conduction. Also, being held in Tashkent in cooperation with a number of international companies since 1997 and intercession "of oil and gas of Uzbekistan – OGU (oil and Turkish war of

Undp)" international exhibition, enterprise network, are important in terms of development and deepening of market relations.

Of uzbekistan state and the oil and gas industry in the development of cooperation with foreign companies to the formation of the initial years of independence comes on. In this regard, the initial state of the cooperation of the largest enterprises in malaysia ", which is proba bx sd" with the company are established. In particular, in cooperation with the company in 1994, the joint venture was established [3] today, also effective on the basis of their activities continues.

A state visit to Malaysia in 2005 of the government of the republic of uzbekistan within the framework of the cooperation to a new level of mastering the study of oil and gas deposits and signing service who come to[4] in this regard is of great importance. In recent years as a result of this agreement, a number of enterprises in the sector of malaysia, uzbekistan the active participation in the implementation of various projects can be observed. In particular, "Petroliam Nasional Berhad ("PETRONAS Car Overseas Sdn.Bh.")"since 2005 korporasiyasi "Uzmeliomashlizing" WHAT has been working in collaboration with[5]. Also, the corporation "Uzmeliomashlizing" WHAT neftgazkimyo signed a memorandum on mutual cooperation in the field between industry, established groups working together on his part, and sent to start work with engineering companies specialized lisenziatlari technological processes[6]. It should be noted that the oil and gas company operating in the field corporation in the world merges at the 500 units of[7], and the leading international organization. The corporation is a holding company focusing on the territory of surkhandarya region since 2006, with mt structured on the basis of geological section and Surkhon promising in the area working on the study. By the corporation in order to carry out this work "PETRONAS operating company llc" and "Car PETRONAS (Surkhanski) operating company LLC" was established as a company. Also, the corporation owned the part of the aral sea in uzbekistan and the search of hydrocarbon deposits are participating in the project carried out for the purpose of mastering. This corporation your share in the project

is 20 percent. In addition, in march 2009, "Uzmeliomashlizing" WHAT configured with mt, in accordance with the ustyurt region Urga by the corporation, and the implementation of the project on development of qanish akchalak mining mining group[8]. Mining and extraction of raw materials from the corporation not only in the field of geological prospecting in uzbekistan, but also in the implementation of important projects in the field of processing of raw materials also are participating. In particular, the decision of the president of the republic of uzbekistan, [9], in accordance with the corporation and shurtan gas chemical complex in the etilen the expansion of production of polyethylene, as well as south africa, "SASOL" of the engagement of the company[10] taken from the shurtan gas chemical complex, cleaned from meta, synthetic (artificial liquid) fuel (GTL) construction of the production plant of the project is carrying out development and implementation activities. As it is known, in this regard, on 14 June 2009, "Petronas" korporasiyasi vice-president of the republic of south africa and Nasaruddin Dat "SASOL"lean strausning during a visit to the country general manager of the company, specialize in the production of artificial liquid fuel on the signing of the agreement setting up the joint venture was important[11].

Artificial liquid fuel in the same place (ss balm), it is necessary to dwell on. Ss balm as a result of converting natural gas to gasoline and diesel fuel products on the market today and the world will be taken a leading oil and gas – upon exx, mobile, SASOL, Shell, Syntroleum technology companies like it has to. Currently, the company building the plant on the production of balm in qatar, ss sasol continues. SASOL company "PETRONAS" korporasiyasi and "Uzmeliomashlizing" WHAT shurtan gas chemical complex in collaboration with the project after the completion of Uzbekistan the state of qatar in the world with a number of the largest manufacturer of artificial fuel is converted to natural gas from the state[12]. The implementation of this project to expand on the basis of the processing of oil, natural gas allows saving of raw materials.

Conclusion words in Uzbekistan the developing of cooperation in the sphere of oil and gas from year to year, has served for the development of the activities of the network. He also said that it must be structured in accordance with Mt, extraction of the raw material gas is distributed in a 50/50 manner, i.e., in favour of Uzbekistan equal to half of the product is given.

References:

1. I. Karimov. Uzbekistan deepening of economic reforms in the way. – T.: Uzbekistan, 1995. – B. 115.
2. A. Obidov in the way of industry and national development: oil and gas of Uzbekistan // the voice of Uzbekistan, 1999, to August 3.
3. H. Nabiev. Innovation sustain oil and gas development networks in the region: economic science. - T., 2008. – B. 61.
4. A. Boboev. Uzbekistan-Malaysia: new page of cooperation // the voice of Uzbekistan on 18 November 2008.
5. Asanov L. "OGU-2008": "skvajina" perspektiv // Delovoy Partner.uz. 21 Maya 2008 g. № 20(737). – S. 3.
6. Republic of Uzbekistan, Respublika of President of "PETRONAS" (Malayziya) korporasiyasi search works with geology, mining and production and prosperous and to make neftgazkimyoni in the field of development to continue cooperation on measures to sustainpp-854 the number will decide. 02.05.2008 y. // The package of the legislation of the republic of Uzbekistan – t., 2009. No. 46. – B. 32.
7. Thus the O. Uzbekistan: vekovoy op promishlennoy dobichi lipid oil // market, money v. f. credit. 2010. № 5. – B. 52. 49-52.
8. In the same place. – B. 49-52.
9. The president of the republic of Uzbekistan "PETRONAS" (Malaysia) geology korporasiyasi search works, mining and the production of

- neftgazkimyoni prosperity and development on measures to continue cooperation in the field of PP-resolution of 854. 02.05.2008 y. // The package of the legislation of the republic of uzbekistan – t., 2009. No. 46. – B. 33.
10. Do uzbekistana v neftegazoviy 2015 goda sector budun vlojeni 21,5 billion. dollarov investment // Delovoy Partner.uz 21 Maya 2009 g. – S. 2.
11. <http://uza> November mid-November.tr/uzb/news/uzbekistan_news/oil_gas_industry_new_taking a dip in_directory.mg
- 12.A. Sadritdinov development trends in the oil and gas industry // the market, money and credit. 2008. № 06(133). – B. 62. 59-62.